

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DIVINE LOVE IN THE CREATION OF MUHAMMAD FÜZULI AND A CHANT OF PURE LOVE

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Abstract

The article discusses Muhammad Fuzuli's philosophy of love and its main essence. It is shown that an important part of the artistic heritage of the artist, which is extensive in volume, is the works on the theme of love. His philosophy of love has its own characteristics. The works written on this subject can be mainly grouped along two lines: examples dedicated to worldly love, that is, metaphorical love; examples of divine love, that is, true love.

The poet's philosophy of love finds its artistic expression mostly in his ghazals and the poem "Leyli and Majnun". Most of the examples of love-themed poetry in the artist's work derive from the "unity-body" philosophy of Sufism. In other words, it rests on divine love. According to Fuzuli, true love is love for a divine being. A person should love the beings in the material world, including his fellow man, as a particle of the divine world, that is, the world of unity.

Keywords: Muhammad Fuzuli, literature, philosophy of love, divine love, pure love, artistic thinking, spiritual world, power of love, love and madness, love and admiration, love and drunkenness, love and shame, etc.

Muhammad Fuzuli, a magician of artistic words, is recognized as one of the most talented representatives of lyrical poetry worldwide. As he said, "shairi-Museyi-kalam" ("Musa kalam poet") created a miracle from a single word, and as the author of unique lyrical (and epic) works, he took a leading position among the artists who became the pride of world poetry. Whether it is meaning-content, form, language-stylistic beauty, musical tone and tone, aesthetics, "word game" and system of metaphors, logical communication and unity within the text, etc. it rose to its highest, honorable and incredible level with the pen of this Azerbaijani artist.

According to Fuzuli, all beings in the material world, including man, are a particle separated from the divine world and fallen into the material world. Since the human soul is given the love of the body by God, at the necessary moment, it leaves the divine world and descends to the world we live in and unites with the body, the material body, takes a copy and image. However, this world turns into a land of suffering and hardship for him, a "night of separation" ("shabi-hijran"). That's why he is throbbing with desire, desire and love to return to his original self. That is, in the presence of the spirit that gives life to man and belongs to the divine world, there is a feeling of infinite love for the original world from which he left and came. Therefore, he wants to return to the world of eternal unity, the land of happiness. In a word, Fuzuli understands and preaches the way of love ("tariqi-esq") as the only means to reach God. This issue is the main essence of the philosophy of love of the philosopher artist. In the poet's philosophical interpretation, it is specially emphasized that this supreme truth can be understood not by the ignorant, the ignorant, but only by the wise, the open-minded, and the perfect. These issues mentioned in the article and its philosophical essence are interpreted on the basis of specific examples from the poet's work.

In the theme gallery of the artist's work, the main colors and shades are related to love. Love is the foundation and yeast of Fuzuli's lyrics. He is known first and foremost as a love poet. The best genius thinker himself explains the reason for this. The lyricist addresses his "I" and declares that it is not worth expecting poems of praise and blame from him. The words of the perfect people who are in love should be loving:

Don't ask me, Fuzuli, to praise me.

I am in love, my word is always love (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

Fuzuli's divan's first poem in Azerbaijani Turkish - "Qad Anarel..." ghazal is also about love.

This ghazal is, in a way, the bismillah of Fuzuli divan. That is, it contains the main idea load and thematic direction of the poet's lyrics. And here we are talking about Sufi love. The poet takes the mystical shades of love as a basis, that is, true love. It is the main condition for the people of perfection to be the master of the path of truth, to know the secret of unity, to accept the reality of the Truth itself, not the vastness of existence (all creation except God) and to live with the pleasure of love with this understanding. Because the poet does not imagine that there is a path to virtue and wisdom other than love:

O Fuzuli, I do not want to abandon-taryk-eskh who,

This virtue makes me inwardly perfect (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

The lyrical hero of our genius thinker does not see love as a worldly passion. This hero of a philosophical nature approaches the issue in a broader way, with the expectation of gnosis. He is free from the sorrow of love ("Giriftari-gami-esq olali azadeyi-dahram"), that is, he is free from all other concerns of the property

world. Because he fell into the sea of love, he forgot the pleasure of the world ("You fell in love with the sea, oh tongue, forget the pleasure of the world"). That is why it is "pleasant with love". According to him, the work of those who burn in the fire of hell is easier than those who burn in the fire of love. Because those who burn in hell, burn once in the fire and save their lives. And the fire of love is constant torment. But the punishment is great. This is an eternal destiny, which was given to the lyrical hero at the beginning of the dawn of love ("safayi-eshq"), at the time of the creation of his soul. The pain of love is such a sublime feeling because of this lover that the one who tries to cure it is like the enemy of that lover:

Love comes with trouble, a lover's temperament is independent,

It is my enemy, friends, who is the mediciner in this trouble (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

The ghazal "I was tired of the soul..." occupies a special place among Fuzuli's love-themed lyrical works. The poem has impressive content, clear idea, flowing language, beautiful style, perfect artistic form. The author was able to create a proportional harmony of content and external effect here.

The ghazal is told in the first person - the language of the lyrical hero. This lover expresses the hero's inner feelings and complaints about his soul in a simple and convincing way. The fact that the poem is based entirely on artistic questions and internal rhyme, i.e. saj', makes its poetic aura even more beautiful. The declaration of the lover's complaint and inner impression is so simple, sincere, and figurative that it convinces the reader. It affects his emotions and aesthetically pleases him:

He made me tired of the soul, isn't he tired of suffering?

The stars have burned out, won't the candle of my wish burn?

The soul of Gamu Bimarin is the best medicine for pain.

Why don't you give me medicine, don't you think I'm sick? (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

The lover, who suffers from the long agony of love, is bored to death. His sigh burns the stars (exaggeration), but the candle of his wishes does not burn. However, the lover does not tire of his suffering. The complaint of the lonely lover is also that the soul provides a cure for the pain of all those who love him. Only this lover is indifferent. However, his burden of love is heavier than others. Of course, God is meant here by the living being.

A lover who hides his love grief reveals it to his lover with the advice of others. However, he does not see loyalty and grace from it. Since he falls on "Shabi-hijran" ("night of separation"), that is, he leaves his family, his job is to live the suffering of this hijran. Here, when the poet says "shabi-hijran", he means the mood of a particle that is separated from its original essence - the divine world. Because the particle that is

separated from the unity and fell into the material world cries because of this separation. Yara longs to be reunited with her true self. This explanation is related to love in Sufism and "Shabi-Hijran" philosophy. Thus, according to Sufism, the human soul (divine "I"), separated from its reality and reunited with the physical body, falls into "shabi-hijran" in the material world, suffers torment and cries out for it.

In the ghazal, Fuzuli's imagery, abundance and fullness of metaphors attract attention. Of course, this enriches the artistic quality of the ghazal and increases its poetry.

Bloody running water from my eyes next to Guli-rukhsarina,

My dear, this is the season, don't the running waters get cloudy? (Fuzuli, I c., 2005)

several eloquent devices are used in the verse. Artistic question - is it not blurred?; saj` (internal rhyme) - neighbor, water, this; artistic address - habibim; epithet - guli-rukhsar (rose face); exaggeration - bloody running water from my eyes; talil or illat: (This is such a poetic figure that any event, concept, process causes the emergence of another event, concept, process, etc. That is, the existence of one concept and event, the creation of another concept and event, appears as the cause and effect of the case). In the first verse of the verse, against the lover's rose face (because her face is like a rose and the color of the rose is red), water flows from the lover's eyes with blood (that is, red in color); allusion (metonymy) - season-flower. The season of spring is not mentioned, but it is clear that spring is meant by that expression; simile - the bloody water flowing from the lover's eyes is compared to the muddy water flowing in the spring. The poet is not so inclined to describe the external beauty of the charmer in the ghazal. However, he resorts to such a method of persuasion that the lover is ashamed of the reproach he made when he sees the unsuspecting soul who loves that soul, who is his "rindu shayda".

The poem also touches on the philosophy of love and shame in the sense of Sufism. The main essence of this philosophical view is that it is impossible to hide love in the heart. He inevitably exposes himself to the world. Therefore, people of love should always be disgraced and should be known among the people as the devil of love:

Fuzuli is always a disgrace to the people.

Who is the question, what is this deal, isn't he tired of this deal? (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

M.Fuzuli's lyrical hero is a philosopher in love. At the level of love, this lyrical hero's relation to body, soul and spirit is based on religious and Sufi-mystical sources. Rather, the lover forgets his physical existence, thinks it does not exist. He is also ready to sacrifice it entirely to the soul. Because not only the body, but also the soul itself belongs to the soul. A lover who has risen to the level of enlightenment loves his soul only because of his soul. He does not think that there is a truth other than the soul in the world of testimony (and in general, existence), including his body and soul.

In the lower layer, in the inner sense of the meaning, the soul mentioned is actually the divine substance - the Truth itself, to which everything belongs. Habib's love for his soul also stems from his concern for his beloved. The wise love their lives for their lives, and the ignorant love their lives for their lives:

He who loves his soul for his soul's sake loves his soul,

Whoever loves his life for his life, loves his life (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

In relation to love, our philosopher-poet sometimes thinks like a Sufi, but sometimes he approaches it from a real, worldly position. In other words, Fuzuli accepts metaphorical love as well as real love. The artist justifies this with such a philosophical-poetic logic that the metaphor is connected to the truth. More precisely, the metaphor is the shining, the dawn of the rays of the sun of truth (physical-absolute) and, therefore, it is not beyond it. Its existence depends on:

Of the blessings, O counsellor, do not make me who I am,

Pertovi-Anvari-Khurshidi-truth is a metaphor (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

In Fuzuli's world of love and wisdom, love and hijran, love and exile, the desperation of love pain, love and infatuation, love and admiration, love and drunkenness, love and shame, love and reproach, love and trouble, love and grief, crying, etc. we find related artistic-philosophical nuances, poetic declarations, intellectual insinuations. In fact, these are specific lines established in the system of views of the Sufism sect. In the gnostic thought, each of them has its own interpretation and meaning about love. Fuzuli's artistic idioms and savings also get their nourishment from here.

The essence of those philosophical categories in our thinking artist and in Sufism in general can be very succinctly interpreted as follows:

Love and hijran: The lover (particle) who is separated from the divine world, from his original essence (unity), descends to the material world and becomes lonely. This is "shabi-hijran" ("night of separation") for him. The time he lives in the world of martyrdom is in proportion to the world of hell, "sustenance-doom" because of the lover:

I knew that the night of the Hijran was the night of Hell

Who, Ruzi-Qiyamat is tomorrow's Shabi-Hijran (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

Love and Vusal: Love is the only way out of Hijran and meeting the Truth. Love is a bridge, a direct means of communication between a servant and God, without intermediaries (without the help of someone else). But the one who is in the wishful thinking should forget both his physical reality, the world and the blessings of the world, and, in general, the massif. A steadfast lover must destroy his physical existence with the

pleasure of Dildar's meeting, in order to reach the eternal state of "seeing-state", the permanent presence of the physical-absolute:

I destroyed your language with pleasure and sight,
They say that the state is permanent, the state is visible (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

Fuzuli's lyrical hero says in his ghazal "Dwelling O Nightingale..." that, O Muslims, if my place were "yar kuyi" (tomorrow's abode), if I were inclined to Rovzei-Rizvan, I would be an infidel. In other words, on the level of belief of Sufism, for the people of wisdom and perfect love, directly reaching tomorrow's destination is even better than achieving the bliss of heaven.

The helplessness of love pain: If love is true, in other words, if it is the immortal grace of God instilled in the soul, "I" of the human body, then there is no cure or remedy for it. It is impossible to erase it from the human heart:

Whatever ails you, there is a cure in the world.

Love is such a difficult pain that it cannot be treated (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

Love and intoxication: Love for a true lover is a source of feiz. He must be intoxicated by the pleasure of this drug. From Majn to the lyrical hero in Fuzuli's poems, those who bear the title of lover are, as a rule, drunk on love. Any number of examples can be cited from the poet's works. He often talks about mey (the wine of divine wisdom and virtue) and meykhana (the place where the truths of God are studied, the inn). These are, of course, philosophical-metaphorical concepts and artistic idioms related to the symbolism of Sufism.

Love and disgrace: It is impossible to keep the secret of love hidden in the heart. Because the intensity, degree, scale and nature of true love is such that it should overflow from the world of the heart, it should be promiscuous and overwhelming. The fate of a true lover is disgrace. Fuzzy:

It is impossible to make people happy and love,
Fall in love and you will be a disgrace in the world (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

This is exactly what he means in his verse. We often find this conclusion in medieval gnostic poetry. For a true lover, shame is a standard, a characteristic vital-moral and spiritual-psychological indicator. In a word, "Love is not pretentious, Risvay should always be in love" (Fuzuli, II c., 2005).

O Fuzuli, I am the sultan of the domain of rebuke, the lightning of my anger is a golden crown, and my silver tears are an ivory throne.

In the 2nd stanza of the poem, the poet skilfully makes use of the plural, which is a type of metaphor belonging to Eastern poetics (this is a type of metaphor in which two or more signs, characteristics, concepts are attributed to the same subject, combined in the same subject), simile and exaggeration.

Love and trouble (torment): The greater the joy of the pleasure of love, the greater the humiliation. If the

lover does not suffer on the path of his love (and does not want it), then he cannot be considered a true lover, nor will he be blessed with vasa joy. The more troubles and hardships a lover suffers in the field of love, the more he proves the reality and greatness of his love. Therefore, a true lover always wishes to be "acquainted with trouble-love" in the world of possessions (the world of Hijran). In short, the hero of the gnosis thinks that the value of the vassa cannot be known without suffering the hardships of the Hijran world. The darkness and pain of separation from the Lord (from the original substance to which the lover belongs) revealed the most mysterious secrets to the wise lover:

I didn't know Wasl without the hardship of Hijran.
Darkness-Hijr made a very mysterious work clear
(Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

The present world is also a world of trials and tribulations for the lover, the measure of which is the burden of suffering and sorrow.

Love and grief (crying): A lover who is separated from his original nature - Yar and fell into "shabi-hijran" (a particle) is condemned to grief and crying in the world of possessions. Because in the existing world, there cannot be absolute, constant joy, comfort and joy (although there is, this is why). The suffering of Hijran and the longing for vasa makes the lover fall into grief, toil, misery, and misery. Fuzuli's lover is also a subject of the explained belief and faith. It is the scale of the scale of effort in the market of love, "Gafilasalari-carivani-gam":

Scales-adjustment-market-market-love fill,
My eyes are always full, my head is like a thousand stones every hour (Fuzuli, I c., 2005).

The result. It is known that in the medieval Islamic world, one of the main problems that engaged fiction as a means of education and spiritual and moral agitation was the question of man and his attitude. In the social-aesthetic, philosophical-ideological practice of artistic thought, the human race was considered an ideal creature. Humanism, the art of speech, which treated man with this higher intention and placed him above all creatures in creation, consistently followed and promoted philanthropy as an important mission. This merit is also clearly manifested in Fuzuli's poetry. Also, the fact that our thinker poet is a more professional and powerful pen holder stands as high in his work as the level of his art compared to his predecessors and successors.

In the work of a humanist artist, man is the most valuable creature in existence. His honor, majesty and beauty are worthy of all praise. In general, as in Eastern literature, in Fuzuli, the highest position after God belongs to human beings. In the poet's lyrics, the definition of the glory and beauty of God begins with the definition of human glory and beauty on a micro scale. However, it is worth noting that, as in Sufi poetry, in Fuzuli, the human race is divided into two groups in terms of perfection and ignorance: the perfect person and the ignorant person. Of course, in the artistic and philosophical evaluation, the place, position and level of these people are sharply distinguished from each other. In exchange for the highness of the first, the cheapness of the second is brought into consideration. Man is called to spiritual and moral perfection, to understand his beauty, dignity and honor. This is one of the main rocks that Fuzuli poetry follows. According to the poet, it is impossible to "produce honorable poetry" with ignorance. For this, it is necessary to reach a mystical rank. The main way of this is related to love and passes through the field of love. In short, the journey of love and the mission of falling in love constitute the main essence and pillar of Fuzuli's philosophy of love. Also, this journey is a mystical journey based on divine love.

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